

A procedure for determining the mating status of the yellow stem borer

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Determining the mating status of a female insect (i.e., whether the insect has mated and, if so, how many times) is important for various studies of insect ecology and pest management. We are studying strategies to delay the evolution of yellow stem borer, *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), adaptation to *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) toxins in transgenic rice (Cohen et al 1997). One of our activities is to examine the timing of mating in relation to adult dispersal to determine whether *Bt*-resistant insects will mate at random with susceptible insects emerging from non-*Bt*

“refuge” fields (Gould 1998). The mating status of a female Lepidopteran is generally determined by examining the bursa copulatrix (a storage sac for sperm) for the presence of a spermatophore (a packet of sperm transferred by the male during mating). Kapur (1964) and Chakravorty (1986) provided a partial description of the reproductive organs of *S. incertulas* but did not describe the appearance of the spermatophore. This note provides a full description of the spermatophore and the female reproductive organs to assist researchers in determining the mating status of female *S. incertulas*.

Female adult *S. incertulas* were collected from a greenhouse-reared colony and from light traps located in the field and were dissected in the laboratory under a dissecting microscope. To obtain virgin females, female pupae were collected from the colony and kept separate from males. Figure 1 shows the arrangement of the female reproductive organs. We deduced the female mating status from the shape of the bursa copulatrix and the presence or absence of a spermatophore within the bursa. The posterior one-third of the abdomen was removed using dissecting scissors and placed in a petri dish containing 70% alcohol. The bursa copulatrix was teased out from the abdomen by pulling the ovipositor out with fine-pointed forceps and holding the rest of the abdomen steady with a needle.

The bursa copulatrix of a virgin female is translucent, collapsed, and cup-shaped (Fig. 2). The bursa of a mated female is glossy, distended, and bulb-shaped with a milky content (Fig. 2). The bursa of a mated female that has laid eggs (Fig. 2) again becomes collapsed and is more sclerotized than the bursa of virgin and mated females. The spermatophore can be seen if the bursa is teased open (Fig. 2). Opening the bursa to look for a spermatophore can provide confirmation of the mating status of a female if this cannot be confidently determined from the shape of the bursa.

Fig. 1. Reproductive structures of female *Scirpophaga incertulas*: (A) ovary, (B) common oviduct, (C) accessory gland, (D) accessory gland reservoir, (E) ostium oviductus (ovipositor), (F) spermathecal gland, (G) spermatheca, (H) bursa copulatrix, (I) ostium bursae (vulva).

Fig. 2. The bursa copulatrix and spermatophore of *S. incertulas*: (A) bursa copulatrix of virgin female, (B) bursa copulatrix of mated female, (C) bursa copulatrix of mated female that had laid eggs, (D) spermatophore after removal from bursa copulatrix.

References

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A genomic library of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* in the broad host range mobilizing *Escherichia coli* strain S17-1

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We used molecular genetic techniques to identify virulence functions of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*). These studies are being conducted on an *Xoo* strain (BXO1) that belongs to a pathotype (Ib) that is widely distributed in India. Functional complementation of virulence-deficient *Xoo* mutants by mobilizing a genomic library of BXO1 (Rajagopal et al 1996) requires the transfer of many individual clones into each mutant strain.

Gene transfer into the BXO1 strain by triparental matings, wherein a plasmid (pRK600) in the helper *E. coli* strain provides the mobilization functions required in *trans*, was extremely low (1 cfu 10^9 recipient cells) and often resulted in a lack of transconjugants. This suggested the presence of a restriction barrier in the BXO1 strain. Two restriction-modification (r-m) systems have been reported from Philippine strains of *Xoo*-*XorI* and *XorII* (Choi and Leach 1994). The isochizomers

of these enzymes are *PstI* and *PvuI*, respectively. Genomic DNA isolated from the BXO1 strain was digested to completion by these enzymes, indicating the absence of *XorI* and *XorII* r-m systems in BXO1.

We assumed that if there indeed existed an r-m system in BXO1, then gene transfer frequencies would be far higher when plasmid DNA was introduced from BXO1 into BXO1 compared with transfer frequencies between *E. coli* and BXO1. Therefore, two random clones from the BXO1 genomic library (pLR17 and pLR18), each with an approximate insert size of 35

kb, were individually mobilized into *Xoo*. Plasmid DNA was isolated separately from the *E. coli* DH5a and *Xoo* strains harboring the pLR17 and pLR18 plasmids. Approximately equal amounts of plasmid DNA were electroporated into competent cells of BXO1. The frequency of electroporation was reduced by at least a thousandfold when plasmid DNA was electroporated from *E. coli* to BXO1 (Table 1). The pLR17 DNA isolated from *E. coli* was also transformed into *E. coli* DH5a competent cells to confirm that there were no deficiencies in transformation from *E. coli* to *E. coli* or

Table 1. Frequency of gene transfer into BXO1.

Donor	Frequency of transformants in BXO1 (no. of kan ^r colonies μg^{-1} of plasmid DNA)
<i>E. coli</i> /pLR17	2.00×10^2
BXO1/pLR17	4.25×10^5
<i>E. coli</i> /pLR18	<1
BXO1/pLR18	3.12×10^5